

Supervisor Incivility and Turnover Intention: Moderating Role of Organizations Support among Employees of Nepali Commercial Banks

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Abstract

The Nepali banking sector is facing serious issues of employees leaving the organisations because of multiple reasons. Among those reasons, the relationship of employees with supervisors has surfaced as an important variable for researchers. Despite the significant role of organisation support (OS), it has not been understood how OS can impact the relationship between supervisor incivility (SI) and turnover intention (TI) among employees. Drawing from the organisation support theory (OST), this paper investigated the moderating role of OS in the relationship between SI and TI among employees of Nepali commercial banks. To achieve the research objective, this paper employed a quantitative approach and a cross-sectional survey research design. Applying the purposive sampling technique, the data were collected from 242 employees. The ordinary least square (OLS) regression and process macro techniques were employed to test the moderated research hypothesis. The results illustrated that SI and OS significantly influence TI. It implies that the increase in SI leads to TI among employees, however, OS decreases the TI among employees. Moreover, OS significantly moderates the relationship between SI and TI. It suggests that employees of Nepali commercial banks intend to leave their respective banks if they experience high SI but if they receive support from the banks TI of employees will decrease significantly. This study offers several insights to human resource (HR) managers that could be helpful to design a performance appraisal mechanism to address the SI in the workplace. Moreover, HR could prepare training and development sessions for employees to empower their employees. This paper argues that this is among the earliest studies to investigate the moderating role of OS with SI and TI. It enriches the existing literature on organisational behavior by applying OST.

Keywords: *moderation analysis, organisation support, supervisor incivility, turnover intention*